

Supplementary Tables:
Glucose Rate-of-Change and Insulin-on-Board
Jointly Weighted Zone Model Predictive Control

Sunil Deshpande, Francis J. Doyle III, Eyal Dassau

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Table S1: Outcomes for induced resistance Scenario A for the proposed controller (QvIOB) versus the reference controller (Qv). Data are shown as mean (standard deviation), the percent time threshold are in mg/dL and the significant effects are highlighted using †.

	Nominal bolus			No bolus			Underestimated bolus			Overestimated bolus		
	QvIOB	Qv	p-value	QvIOB	Qv	p-value	QvIOB	Qv	p-value	QvIOB	Qv	p-value
Mean glucose	154.6(11.4)	158.1(11.9)	< 0.001†	183.5(24.2)	192.2(27.1)	< 0.001†	160.2(12.7)	164.2(13.2)	< 0.001†	149.0(10.8)	152.0(11.1)	< 0.001†
SD glucose	26.5(9.1)	26.2(9.1)	0.017	47.5(14.3)	48.9(14.9)	< 0.001†	30.3(9.4)	29.9(9.4)	0.017	23.4(8.9)	23.2(8.9)	0.152
LBGI	0.0(0.1)	0.0(0.1)	0.206	0.0(0.1)	0.0(0.1)	0.158	0.0(0.1)	0.0(0.1)	0.164	0.0(0.1)	0.0(0.1)	0.306
HBGI	4.4(1.9)	4.8(2.0)	< 0.001†	9.9(4.7)	11.5(5.4)	< 0.001†	5.3(2.2)	5.9(2.3)	< 0.001†	3.5(1.8)	3.9(1.8)	< 0.001†
% < 54	0.0(0.3)	0.0(0.2)	0.614	0.0(0.2)	0.0(0.2)	0.882	0.0(0.3)	0.0(0.2)	0.698	0.0(0.3)	0.0(0.2)	0.841
% < 70	0.0(0.4)	0.0(0.3)	0.660	0.0(0.3)	0.0(0.3)	0.659	0.0(0.4)	0.0(0.3)	0.544	0.0(0.4)	0.0(0.3)	0.945
% ∈ [70, 140]	36.2(13.2)	30.6(13.5)	< 0.001†	27.6(13.6)	20.6(13.3)	< 0.001†	33.4(13.0)	27.5(13.2)	< 0.001†	42.7(14.4)	37.0(14.8)	< 0.001†
% ∈ [70, 180]	81.2(14.3)	78.7(14.7)	< 0.001†	53.5(15.9)	48.9(16.0)	< 0.001†	73.4(14.6)	70.2(14.8)	< 0.001†	87.4(13.2)	85.6(13.8)	< 0.001†
% > 180	18.8(14.3)	21.3(14.7)	< 0.001†	46.5(15.9)	51.1(16.0)	< 0.001†	26.6(14.6)	29.8(14.8)	< 0.001†	12.6(13.2)	14.4(13.8)	< 0.001†
% > 300	0.1(0.6)	0.1(0.7)	0.540	3.1(7.3)	4.5(9.3)	< 0.001†	0.1(1.0)	0.2(1.1)	0.366	0.0(0.4)	0.0(0.5)	0.707
$\sum_k u_{N,k}$	51.0(11.0)	50.0(10.7)	< 0.001†	45.5(7.8)	43.9(7.3)	< 0.001†	49.7(10.3)	48.6(10.0)	< 0.001†	52.4(11.7)	51.5(11.4)	< 0.001†
$\sum_k u_{pb,k}$	36.0(7.2)	34.7(7.0)	< 0.001†	45.5(7.8)	43.9(7.3)	< 0.001†	37.9(7.2)	36.6(7.0)	< 0.001†	34.3(7.2)	33.1(7.0)	< 0.001†
$\sum_k u_{fb,k}$	15.0(6.1)	15.3(6.1)	< 0.001†	0.0(0.0)	0.0(0.0)	—	11.8(4.9)	12.0(5.0)	< 0.001†	18.1(7.2)	18.4(7.2)	0.002
$\sum_k \Delta u_{pb,k} > 0$	11.0(1.7)	9.6(1.7)	< 0.001†	19.5(2.8)	17.7(2.5)	< 0.001†	12.8(1.8)	11.3(1.7)	< 0.001†	9.7(1.7)	8.3(1.7)	< 0.001†
$\sum_k \Delta u_{pb,k} \leq 0$	-2.6(1.0)	-2.5(1.0)	< 0.001†	-1.6(1.1)	-1.5(1.0)	< 0.001†	-2.4(1.0)	-2.2(1.0)	< 0.001†	-3.0(1.1)	-2.8(1.1)	< 0.001†
CVGA zone: A	84	57	—	0	0	—	20	12	—	231	183	—
CVGA zone: B	905	933	—	767	696	—	957	962	—	761	810	—
CVGA zone: C	5	7	—	231	302	—	18	25	—	5	5	—
CVGA zone: D	5	3	—	2	2	—	5	1	—	3	2	—
CVGA zone: E	0	0	—	0	0	—	0	0	—	0	0	—
Overnight												
Mean glucose	129.0(8.2)	133.7(8.8)	< 0.001†	136.6(15.2)	145.3(18.9)	< 0.001†	130.3(9.0)	135.5(9.9)	< 0.001†	128.1(7.9)	132.3(8.3)	< 0.001†
SD glucose	10.4(5.8)	10.4(5.5)	0.852	16.6(10.1)	17.4(10.2)	0.004	11.4(6.5)	11.3(6.2)	0.413	9.7(5.4)	9.6(5.2)	0.865
LBGI	0.0(0.4)	0.0(0.4)	0.485	0.0(0.4)	0.0(0.3)	0.303	0.0(0.4)	0.0(0.3)	0.407	0.0(0.4)	0.0(0.4)	0.527
HBGI	1.0(0.7)	1.4(0.9)	< 0.001†	2.0(2.1)	3.0(2.9)	< 0.001†	1.1(0.9)	1.6(1.1)	< 0.001†	0.9(0.6)	1.2(0.7)	< 0.001†
% < 54	0.0(0.9)	0.0(0.8)	0.943	0.0(0.9)	0.0(0.7)	0.882	0.0(0.9)	0.0(0.8)	0.914	0.0(0.9)	0.0(0.9)	0.972
% < 70	0.0(1.2)	0.0(1.1)	0.978	0.0(1.2)	0.0(1.1)	0.914	0.0(1.2)	0.0(1.1)	0.793	0.0(1.2)	0.0(1.1)	0.979
% ∈ [70, 140]	83.0(17.4)	70.8(23.9)	< 0.001†	70.9(23.9)	52.9(30.7)	< 0.001†	80.4(18.3)	66.9(25.9)	< 0.001†	85.0(16.9)	73.9(23.4)	< 0.001†
% ∈ [70, 180]	99.3(3.5)	99.2(3.9)	0.284	93.3(11.7)	89.4(16.0)	< 0.001†	98.8(4.8)	98.3(5.7)	0.015	99.6(3.0)	99.6(3.0)	0.944
% > 180	0.6(3.3)	0.8(3.8)	0.248	6.7(11.7)	10.5(16.0)	< 0.001†	1.2(4.6)	1.7(5.6)	0.009	0.4(2.7)	0.4(2.7)	0.928
% > 300	0.0(0.0)	0.0(0.0)	—	0.0(0.3)	0.1(1.3)	0.020	0.0(0.0)	0.0(0.0)	—	0.0(0.0)	0.0(0.0)	—
$\sum_k u_{N,k}$	8.6(2.1)	8.3(2.0)	< 0.001†	8.9(2.3)	8.7(2.3)	< 0.001†	8.7(2.1)	8.4(2.1)	< 0.001†	8.6(2.1)	8.2(2.0)	< 0.001†
$\sum_k u_{pb,k}$	8.6(2.1)	8.3(2.0)	< 0.001†	8.9(2.3)	8.7(2.3)	< 0.001†	8.7(2.1)	8.4(2.1)	< 0.001†	8.6(2.1)	8.2(2.0)	< 0.001†
$\sum_k u_{fb,k}$	0.0(0.0)	0.0(0.0)	—	0.0(0.0)	0.0(0.0)	—	0.0(0.0)	0.0(0.0)	—	0.0(0.0)	0.0(0.0)	—
$\sum_k \Delta u_{pb,k} > 0$	2.5(0.7)	2.0(0.6)	< 0.001†	2.6(0.7)	2.2(0.7)	< 0.001†	2.5(0.7)	2.0(0.6)	< 0.001†	2.5(0.7)	2.0(0.6)	< 0.001†
$\sum_k \Delta u_{pb,k} \leq 0$	-1.2(0.5)	-1.0(0.5)	< 0.001†	-1.0(0.5)	-0.8(0.5)	< 0.001†	-1.1(0.5)	-0.9(0.5)	< 0.001†	-1.2(0.6)	-1.0(0.5)	< 0.001†
CVGA zone: A	933	930	—	620	536	—	894	878	—	952	955	—
CVGA zone: B	65	69	—	377	454	—	104	121	—	47	44	—
CVGA zone: C	1	1	—	3	10	—	2	1	—	1	1	—
CVGA zone: D	0	0	—	0	0	—	0	0	—	0	0	—
CVGA zone: E	0	0	—	0	0	—	0	0	—	0	0	—

Table S2: Outcomes for nominal Scenario B for the proposed controller (QvIOB) versus the reference controller (Qv). Data are shown as mean (standard deviation), the percent time threshold are in mg/dL and the significant effects are highlighted using †.

	Nominal bolus			No bolus			Underestimated bolus			Overestimated bolus		
	QvIOB	Qv	p-value	QvIOB	Qv	p-value	QvIOB	Qv	p-value	QvIOB	Qv	p-value
Mean glucose	136.2(8.6)	137.9(8.8)	< 0.001†	156.0(13.8)	161.3(15.6)	< 0.001†	141.8(8.9)	143.9(9.3)	< 0.001†	130.7(8.4)	132.2(8.6)	< 0.001†
SD glucose	30.4(10.1)	30.2(10.0)	0.151	48.9(13.6)	49.8(13.9)	< 0.001†	34.6(10.6)	34.3(10.5)	0.041	27.4(9.6)	27.3(9.6)	0.566
LBGI	0.2(0.3)	0.1(0.2)	< 0.001†	0.2(0.5)	0.1(0.4)	< 0.001†	0.1(0.2)	0.1(0.2)	< 0.001†	0.2(0.3)	0.2(0.3)	0.019
HBGI	2.6(1.4)	2.7(1.5)	< 0.001†	6.0(2.5)	6.7(2.9)	< 0.001†	3.4(1.6)	3.6(1.6)	< 0.001†	2.0(1.3)	2.1(1.3)	< 0.001†
% < 54	0.0(0.4)	0.0(0.4)	0.745	0.1(0.8)	0.1(0.7)	0.065	0.0(0.4)	0.0(0.4)	0.525	0.1(0.6)	0.1(0.6)	0.892
% < 70	0.2(1.0)	0.2(0.9)	0.376	0.5(1.9)	0.3(1.5)	< 0.001†	0.2(1.0)	0.1(0.9)	0.025	0.4(1.4)	0.4(1.4)	0.425
% ∈ [70, 140]	64.5(8.8)	63.2(8.8)	< 0.001†	52.3(8.5)	49.1(9.3)	< 0.001†	58.5(7.6)	56.9(7.8)	< 0.001†	71.1(10.0)	69.9(10.0)	< 0.001†
% ∈ [70, 180]	88.6(10.1)	88.0(10.2)	< 0.001†	69.3(9.7)	66.6(10.4)	< 0.001†	83.3(10.5)	82.4(10.6)	< 0.001†	92.1(9.2)	91.7(9.4)	0.012
% > 180	11.2(9.9)	11.9(10.1)	< 0.001†	30.2(9.6)	33.1(10.4)	< 0.001†	16.5(10.3)	17.5(10.5)	< 0.001†	7.5(8.8)	7.9(9.0)	0.003
% > 300	0.1(0.5)	0.1(0.5)	0.986	1.2(3.7)	1.6(4.3)	< 0.001†	0.1(0.9)	0.2(0.9)	0.866	0.0(0.3)	0.0(0.3)	0.977
$\sum_k u_{N,k}$	40.4(9.2)	39.9(9.0)	< 0.001†	36.7(7.3)	35.6(7.0)	< 0.001†	39.2(8.6)	38.6(8.5)	< 0.001†	41.8(9.7)	41.4(9.6)	< 0.001†
$\sum_k u_{pb,k}$	27.5(6.5)	26.9(6.4)	< 0.001†	36.7(7.3)	35.6(7.0)	< 0.001†	29.4(6.6)	28.6(6.6)	< 0.001†	26.0(6.3)	25.4(6.3)	< 0.001†
$\sum_k u_{fb,k}$	12.9(5.0)	13.0(5.1)	0.156	0.0(0.0)	0.0(0.0)	—	9.8(3.9)	9.9(4.0)	0.025	15.8(6.1)	15.9(6.1)	0.195
$\sum_k \Delta u_{pb,k} > 0$	5.7(1.5)	4.8(1.6)	< 0.001†	13.6(2.3)	12.0(2.1)	< 0.001†	7.1(1.6)	6.0(1.7)	< 0.001†	4.9(1.4)	4.0(1.5)	< 0.001†
$\sum_k \Delta u_{pb,k} \leq 0$	-5.8(1.4)	-5.4(1.3)	< 0.001†	-4.6(1.4)	-4.0(1.4)	< 0.001†	-5.3(1.3)	-5.0(1.3)	< 0.001†	-6.5(1.4)	-6.1(1.4)	< 0.001†
CVGA zone: A	164	153	—	1	0	—	64	60	—	225	229	—
CVGA zone: B	792	808	—	819	804	—	879	893	—	706	709	—
CVGA zone: C	3	4	—	91	116	—	13	16	—	17	12	—
CVGA zone: D	40	34	—	63	62	—	41	28	—	51	49	—
CVGA zone: E	1	1	—	26	18	—	3	2	—	1	1	—
Overnight												
Mean glucose	115.8(6.1)	118.7(6.6)	< 0.001†	116.7(6.5)	121.1(7.5)	< 0.001†	116.0(6.1)	119.0(6.6)	< 0.001†	115.7(6.3)	118.7(7.0)	< 0.001†
SD glucose	10.3(5.4)	10.3(5.5)	0.848	11.3(6.8)	11.5(7.1)	0.381	10.6(5.6)	10.5(5.7)	0.554	10.1(5.3)	10.3(5.5)	0.507
LBGI	0.2(0.4)	0.2(0.4)	< 0.001†	0.3(0.8)	0.2(0.6)	< 0.001†	0.2(0.5)	0.2(0.4)	< 0.001†	0.2(0.5)	0.2(0.4)	< 0.001†
HBGI	0.3(0.3)	0.4(0.4)	< 0.001†	0.3(0.4)	0.6(0.6)	< 0.001†	0.3(0.3)	0.4(0.4)	< 0.001†	0.3(0.3)	0.4(0.4)	< 0.001†
% < 54	0.0(0.7)	0.0(0.5)	0.542	0.2(1.5)	0.1(1.2)	0.255	0.0(0.6)	0.0(0.6)	0.742	0.0(0.7)	0.0(0.7)	0.959
% < 70	0.2(1.8)	0.1(1.5)	0.389	0.6(3.3)	0.4(2.7)	0.028	0.2(1.9)	0.2(1.6)	0.170	0.2(1.9)	0.2(1.7)	0.323
% ∈ [70, 140]	97.1(7.9)	95.7(10.4)	< 0.001†	95.1(9.5)	92.1(12.1)	< 0.001†	96.6(8.2)	95.1(10.7)	< 0.001†	97.3(7.8)	95.6(10.9)	< 0.001†
% ∈ [70, 180]	99.7(2.0)	99.8(2.0)	0.780	99.2(3.8)	99.1(3.8)	0.442	99.6(2.2)	99.7(2.2)	0.482	99.7(2.2)	99.7(2.2)	0.586
% > 180	0.1(1.0)	0.1(1.4)	0.514	0.3(1.8)	0.6(2.7)	0.001	0.1(1.2)	0.1(1.5)	0.581	0.1(1.2)	0.1(1.5)	0.654
% > 300	0.0(0.0)	0.0(0.0)	—	0.0(0.0)	0.0(0.0)	—	0.0(0.0)	0.0(0.0)	—	0.0(0.0)	0.0(0.0)	—
$\sum_k u_{N,k}$	7.0(1.9)	6.8(1.8)	< 0.001†	7.0(1.8)	6.8(1.8)	< 0.001†	7.0(1.8)	6.8(1.8)	< 0.001†	7.1(1.9)	6.9(1.8)	< 0.001†
$\sum_k u_{pb,k}$	7.0(1.9)	6.8(1.8)	< 0.001†	7.0(1.8)	6.8(1.8)	< 0.001†	7.0(1.8)	6.8(1.8)	< 0.001†	7.1(1.9)	6.9(1.8)	< 0.001†
$\sum_k u_{fb,k}$	0.0(0.0)	0.0(0.0)	—	0.0(0.0)	0.0(0.0)	—	0.0(0.0)	0.0(0.0)	—	0.0(0.0)	0.0(0.0)	—
$\sum_k \Delta u_{pb,k} > 0$	1.7(0.6)	1.3(0.5)	< 0.001†	1.7(0.6)	1.2(0.5)	< 0.001†	1.7(0.6)	1.2(0.5)	< 0.001†	1.7(0.6)	1.3(0.6)	< 0.001†
$\sum_k \Delta u_{pb,k} \leq 0$	-2.0(0.6)	-1.7(0.6)	< 0.001†	-1.9(0.6)	-1.7(0.6)	< 0.001†	-2.0(0.6)	-1.7(0.6)	< 0.001†	-1.9(0.6)	-1.7(0.7)	< 0.001†
CVGA zone: A	789	831	—	797	824	—	799	854	—	768	813	—
CVGA zone: B	198	160	—	168	152	—	182	134	—	213	175	—
CVGA zone: C	13	9	—	35	24	—	19	11	—	19	12	—
CVGA zone: D	0	0	—	0	0	—	0	0	—	0	0	—
CVGA zone: E	0	0	—	0	0	—	0	0	—	0	0	—